

Efficacy of Self-Management Technique in Reducing Lateness to School Behaviour Among Secondary School Students in Imo State

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Abstract

This study investigated the efficacy of self-management technique in reducing lateness to school behaviour among secondary school students in Owerri Municipal Council of Imo State. A quasi experimental design which involves a pre-test, post-test and control group method was adopted in this study with two research questions and two hypotheses. The population of the study comprised of 927 SS2 students. The sample for this study comprised of thirty (20) students drawn through purposive sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection in the study was a structured questionnaire titled "Late Coming Identification Scale (LCIS)". The reliability of the research instrument was established using the test-re-test method using Pearson product moment correlation which yielded a coefficient- r of 0.82. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and t -test statistics with the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) ver. 20 to establish the significant difference between the mean scores at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. From data analyzed, it was discovered that self-management technique was significantly effective in reducing lateness to school behaviour among students. Also the study found that self-management technique was significantly more effective in reducing lateness to school behaviour among the female students than the male students. The study recommended among others that counsellors, teachers and psychologists should adopt self-management technique as an effective strategy in reducing lateness to school behaviour among secondary school students.

Key words: Efficacy, Self-management, Technique, Lateness, Behaviour, Students

Introduction

The school (secondary in particular) is considered as a hub for transformational learning and life skills. Students are enrolled not only to acquire knowledge and understanding of the world phenomenon but also to become better citizens and human beings. In this regard, schools through their curriculum inculcate the significance of social skills in the learners in order to aid with the required skills to become responsible beings (Malik, Ladhani & Bhamani, 2013). On other hand, the students and families are equally held responsible for the learning they acquire from the school and attitude and behaviour that exhibit

towards school and learning. Hence, the students in secondary schools are not only assessed for the demonstration of their intellectual capabilities but also their behaviour.

One of the challenging features of secondary school education in Nigeria since independence is students' lateness to school. This trend however, was not easily noticed when boarding schools were prevalent in our educational system. With the proliferation of secondary schools which do not provide boarding facilities, students' lateness to school is on the increase (Wale, 2005). Some of the tasks of the school child are to be able to properly schedule his/her time (time management) for his/her school activities, be conscious of time and follow up punctually (Shore, 2004). Most secondary school students lack this ability which culminates in their being late to school.

Lateness to school behaviour has been identified as one of the most common behavioural problems among our secondary school students today (Chima & Nnodum, 2006). Many reasons such as the problem of transportation, early morning hawking, laziness on the part of the students, domestic duties, which have been attributed to students' late coming to school are mainly home-based and therefore may be directly tackled from the home through the students' determination and self-will to manage their own behaviour, bearing in mind that the primary goal of education is to assist individuals to become more independent in managing their own behaviour.

Okwilagwe (2007) noted that lateness to school behaviour is at the top of the list in the nature and frequency of student's indiscipline in schools. The trend of student's lateness to school often develop into adulthood hence in the larger society, lateness still persists. It features even at state occasions, when key officials arrive sometimes hours behind schedule. It is therefore necessary to check the habit of being late, especially at the early stage of secondary school in order to prevent its formation and consequent adverse effects in future life. Time is like a sword. If you did not cut it, it will cut you. Basically, human beings (students) are the most difficult to manage (Bataneh, 2014). According to Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary (1995), lateness implies a situation where an individual arrives after the proper, scheduled or usual time. However, some students are late to class on a regular basis, and students are probably displaying a sort of defiance or impedance. Thus, students are proper to rationalize excuse, such as, traffic jam, parents' care or job responsibilities that prevent them being punctual attending the class.

According to Chima and Nnodum (2006), lateness to school behaviour not only hampers students' academic output, it is overtly a cog in the wheel of the quest for discipline in our secondary schools. Lateness to school behaviour disrupts the school work in many ways. It affects some of the important and compulsory variables in the school process slated for morning periods on the school time table. However, when students come to class late, it can confuse the flowing of a lecture or discussion, distract other students, and disturb learning teaching process. Moreover, lateness can become frequent and infect other students. However, Schneider (1998) reported that the reality of classroom life may be very different. All faculties are confronted with students who engage in behaviours that are disruptive to the educational process. Secondary school male and female students may be late for class, leave early, talk inappropriately, or sleep during class. Students who are behavioural latecomers absent themselves from morning functions and morning assemblies where instructions are given to students. At times, they absent from some of their lessons and the consequences are always discernable in their learning outcome.

Lateness to school behaviour does not augur well with the "inculcation of the right type of values and attitudes for the survival of the individual and Nigerian society" as stipulated by Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). A school which is known to harbour students who habitual latecomers are is not taken seriously in the academic circles. According to Chima and Nnodum (2006), lateness to school falls under acts of negligence. They went further to report that Ugwuegbulam classified latecomers under concealed, occasional and habitual. Concealed latecomers come to school early but loiter around the school not taking

part in the morning functions as well as the morning assembly. The occasional latecomers come late to school not very often while habitual latecomers come late to school almost every day.

However, the student attendance policy has been developed as a role of the school commitment to provide a supportive learning environment which authorizes all male and female students who have selected to study with the school to fulfil their absolute potential. ETC's (2009) reported that the attendance and punctuality policy clearly states that "regular and punctual attendance is of paramount importance in ensuring that all students have full access to the curriculum. Valuable learning time is lost when students are absent or late". Therefore, schools expect students to attend all learning and teaching sessions. Thus, students should come on time for classes. Late arrival students are disruptive and inequitable to other class members. Basically, there are a number of hidden reasons that make students arrive to class late, which causes the source of the problem. Nonetheless, instructors have not yet established appropriate dealing strategies to uproot such behaviour.

Therefore, students' lateness to school behaviour is considered as an educational problem and epidemic diseases which spread and infect other students, and lead to delayed follow-up curriculum and become chronic among students. As we know there are a number of possible reasons that make students to come to class late. Several methods have been used to tackle the problem of late coming in schools, ranging from punishment to luring pupils with new incentives. In Nigeria, school administrators resort to locking of school gate after 8:00a.m, flogging, picking or weeding around the school compound. Despite all these actions secondary school students continue to be late to school. There is the need therefore, to try to identify other approaches like the use of self-management technique that could possibly stop lateness to school by students in Nigeria and this study is one of such efforts.

In view of the problems posed by late-coming behaviour, there is need to modify the misbehaviour. This can be achieved through some therapeutic strategies such as self-management technique. According Oguzie, Obi and Nnadi (2019), self-management technique is defined as a behaviour intervention strategy which is used to help clients to achieve adequate self-awareness and self-control. Self-management technique is a counselling therapy that has been used to modify behavioural problems such as truancy, nonchalant attitude and lateness to school. Self-management involves the student marking their own behaviour, positive or negative, and consulting with a teacher to verify their responses (Zlomke & Zlomke, 2003). Studies have revealed the use of self-management technique in treating some behavioural and psychological problems of learners (Olorunfemi-Olabisi and Akomolafe, 2013; Oguzie, Obi & Nnadi, 2019). The need, therefore, to assist students with late coming behaviour cannot be over emphasized. Self-management can be used to give students more control and responsibility. Based on these expositions, the researchers intended to investigate the efficacy of self-management technique in the reduction of lateness to school behaviour among secondary school students in Owerri Municipal Council of Imo State.

Purpose of the Study

The main aim of this study was to examine the efficacy of self-management technique in reducing lateness to school behaviour among secondary school students in Owerri Municipal of Imo State. Specifically, the study ascertained:

1. The difference between the pretest and posttest lateness to school behaviour mean scores of secondary school students treated with self-management technique and those in the control group.
2. The difference between the pretest and posttest lateness to school behaviour mean scores of male and female secondary school students treated with self-management technique.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the difference between the pretest and posttest lateness to school behaviour mean scores of secondary school students treated with self-management technique and those in the control group?
2. What is the difference between the pretest and posttest lateness to school behaviour mean scores of male and female secondary school students treated with self-management technique?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest lateness to school behaviour mean scores of secondary school students treated with self-management technique and those in the control group.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the pretest and posttest lateness to school behaviour mean scores of male and female secondary school students treated with self-management technique.

Method

This study is a quasi experimental study which adopts a pre-test, post-test and control group method with a 2x2 matrix. There are two rows consisting of treatment strategy of Self-Management Technique (SM) and the control group. There are also two columns reflecting the gender of the participants as either male or female. The researchers adopted a factorial design because of the fact that the design accomplishes in one experiment what otherwise might require two or more separate studies. Apart from this fact, the design also provides opportunity to study the interacting effect of the moderating variable.

2x2 Factorial design

Treatment	Gender					
	Boys			Girls		
SM	O1	T	O2	O1	T	O2
Control	O1	-	O2	O1	-	O2

Key

- T = Treatment
- = No treatment
SM = Self-management technique
C = Control group
O1 = Pre-test
O2 = Post-test

The population of this study comprised of (927) SS2 students from all the senior secondary schools identified as late comers in Owerri Municipal Council. The sample for this study comprised of twenty (20) SS2 students drawn from the population through purposive sampling technique. The subjects that were used for the study are those who had existing record of late coming behaviour cases.

The instrument used for data collection in this study was the Late Coming Identification Scale (LCIS). The instrument is a twenty (20) item pencil and paper scale. Items on this scale were designed by the researchers from the characteristics of late-coming behaviours exhibited by students as pointed out by Pope (2003) and Malik, Ladhani and Bhamani (2013). It is made up of two sections; A and B. Section A elicited information on students Bio-data. Section B on the other hand, comprised of twenty late coming traits related items. The response system was a three point scale of “Always”, “Sometimes” and “Rarely”; quantified as 3, 2, 1 respectively and were positively structured. A high score range of 40 - 60, indicated late coming. These scores were used as a parameter for identifying late coming behaviour of students, so only those that scored 20 and above were selected for the confirmatory test. The LCIS was validated by two experts from guidance and counselling and one expert in educational measurement and evaluation, and the reliability was established using the test-re-test reliability approach. Here, the instrument was

administered on 30 selected participants that were not part of the study and then re-administered on the same participants after a period of two weeks. Scores from the first and second tests were correlated using Pearson “r” correlation coefficient method which produced an index of 0.82 which was considered enough for the study.

Two research assistants participated in the study. In the collection of data for this study, the instrument was administered on face-to-face to the participants in order to collect them back after responding to the items on the scale. The researchers introduced themselves to the form teachers and explained their mission in order to get their assistance. In doing this, the researchers introduced themselves to the selected students, explained their mission; the purpose of gathering them in a group and then assures them of confidentiality. They established rapport with the students and familiarized with them by allowing them to introduce themselves to them.

The experimental group was treated with self-management technique, while the control group received no treatment. After the experiment, the LCIS instrument was reshuffled and re-administered to the experimental and control groups respectively. The participants’ responses were then scored and the overall data generated were subjected to statistical analysis. Mean was used to answer the research questions, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Table 1: Mean scores of the participants (SM and control) at pre-test and post-test assessment periods.

Test Group	Pre-test			Post-test	
	N	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD
Self Management (SM)	10	44.9	2.77	23.0	2.54
Control Group	10	46.1	1.97	45.5	2.17

Table 1: shows the mean scores of the participants (SM and control) at pre-test and post-test assessment periods. It shows that the students experimentally treated with self-management technique had a pre-test mean score of 44.9 and a post-test mean score of 23.0, while students under the control group had a pre-test and post-test mean score of 46.1 and 45.5 respectively. The result showed that at pre-test, the students under the experimental group and control groups had close means but at post-test, the mean scores were reduced for the experimental group but was still high by the control group. Hence, the conclusion is that self-management technique was effective in reducing lateness to school behaviour among the secondary school students.

Table 2: Mean scores of the male and female participants exposed to self-management (SM) at post-test assessment period.

Test	Post-test		
Self Management (SM)	N	\bar{X}	SD
Male	5	24.4	3.05
Female	5	21.6	0.55

Table 2 shows the mean scores of the male and female participants exposed to self-management (SM) at post-test assessment period. The table showed that the male students under the self-management technique had a mean of 24.4 while their female counterparts scored an average mean of 21.6. This implies

that self-management technique was more effective in reducing lateness to school among female students than their male counterparts.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for the significant difference between the mean scores of the participants (SM and control) at pre-test and post-test assessment periods.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects					
Dependent Variable: PRE TEST					
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	14.627 ^a	2	4.876	.808	.501
Intercept	202.500	1	202.500	33.562	.000
POSTTEST	7.427	1	7.427	1.231	.277
TREATMENT	6.797	1	3.398	.563	.576
Error	156.873	17	6.034		
Total	62279.000	20			
Corrected Total	171.500	19			

a. R Squared = .085 (Adjusted R Squared = -.020)

Table 3 above displayed the result gotten in respect of hypothesis 1. From the table, the f-calculated value for post test effect was 1.231 with significance probability of 0.277, which is greater than 0.05. This indicates that the group effect is significant at 5% level of significance ($P < 0.05$). This showed a significant difference among the two groups. The researchers therefore rejected the null hypothesis and accepted the alternative hypothesis that is to say there is a significant difference between the mean scores of the participants (SM and control) at pre-test and post-test assessment periods.

Table 4: T-test analysis of difference between the mean scores of the male and female participants treated with self management (SM) at post-test assessment period.

Self Management	N	\bar{X}	S.D	Df	T_{cal}	T_{tab}	Decision
Male	5	24.4	3.05				
Female	5	21.6	0.55	18	2.02	1.96	Reject Ho

Table 4 gave the mean score and standard deviations of male students treated with self-management technique as 24.4 and 3.05 respectively with that of the female students treated with self management technique mean scores and standard deviations as 21.6 and 0.55 respectively. At 18 degree of freedom, with application of the t-test calculated, its result of 2.02 is greater than the t-tabulated at 5% level of significance, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is significant difference between the mean scores of the male and female participants exposed to self-management technique (SM) at post-test assessment period.

Discussion

The finding of this study revealed that self-management technique was effective in reducing lateness to school behaviour among secondary school students in Owerri Municipal Council of Imo State. It further established that there is significant difference between the mean scores of the participants (SM

and control) at pre-test and post-test assessment periods. This implies that students in the experimental group had a significant reduction in their lateness to school behaviour. This finding of the study is in-line with the previous report by Chima and Nnodum (2006) who found that self-management technique was significantly effective in treating lateness to school among students. Similarly, the results of the study by Malik, Ladhani and Bhamani (2013) revealed a significant change in the students' tardiness in the school post intervention. In support of the above finding also, Oguzie, Obi and Nnadi (2019) after the study on recommended that Guidance counsellors and psychologists should adopt self-management technique as an effective intervention measure in treating maladaptive behaviours among secondary school students. These findings highlight the importance of a relationship between institutional practices of reward and behaviour modification in students. Perhaps it is in this regard, that previous researchers emphasized that the inculcation and maintenance of desirable behaviours among students are entrusted upon the shoulders of guidance counsellors (Okafor, Obi & Oguzie, 2018; Oguzie & Nwokolo, 2019; Ezunu, Oguzie, Aigbokhaode & Ezunu, 2020). This implies that the need for the use of self-management technique by therapists in treating lateness to school behaviour among students cannot be overemphasized.

Another finding of this study shows that self-management technique is more effective in reducing lateness to school behaviour among the female students than the male students. Also there was significant difference between the mean scores of the male and female participants treated with self-management technique (SM) at post-test assessment period. This is in agreement with Tayo-Olajubutu and Oladipo (2013) result showed that there was a significant difference in the discriminatory behaviour between males and females after treatment. In support of this finding, Oguzie, Ezunu, Uba, Osagie-Obazee (2018) observed that female students often embrace and benefit more from behaviour intervention programs than their male counterparts. More so, the results from the study by Olorunfemi-Olabisi and Akomolafe (2013) showed that self-management technique significantly enhanced the academic self-concept of under achievers in secondary schools especially among the female groups. Wolgemuth, Cobb and Dugan's (2010) findings equally support the efficacy of self-management interventions across educational environments and genders in the improvement of academic performance and correlates of academic achievement (classroom behaviour).

However, this particular finding of the study contradicts the finding by previous researchers (Oguzie, Ani, Obi & Onyegirim, 2018; Oguzie, Obi & Nnadi, 2019) who found that there is no significant gender difference in the effectiveness of self-management technique. One possible reason for the contradiction between this particular finding of this study and that of Oguzie and his group may be as a result of differences in methodological approaches and location.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study and the discussion thereafter, the researchers concluded that self-management technique is significantly effective in reducing lateness to school behaviour among secondary school students. It was also concluded that self-management technique was significantly more effective in reducing lateness to school behaviour among the female students who participated in the experiment than their male counterparts.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. That counsellors, teachers and psychologists should adopt self-management technique as an effective strategy in reducing lateness to school behaviour among secondary school students.
2. Early identification and control of lateness to school behaviour is very important in our school system as this will help to improve students' punctuality to school.
3. Seminar and workshops should be organized for teachers, counsellors and administrators on the need to adopt the use of psychological principles in the management of lateness to school behaviour among

students rather than punishment. They should be exposed to these psychological therapies, skills and application so as to help them manage the lateness.

4. That counsellors and other helping professionals should not bother about gender differences when adopting self-management technique in treating lateness to school behaviour among their clients.

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